

THE IMPORTANCE OF DISCOURSE IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING ENGLISH

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Abstract

The article is devoted to the consideration of the concept of “discourse.” The paper analyzes the main characteristics and types of discourse, defines the specifics of discourse competence, and emphasizes its importance in the process of teaching foreign language communication in the context of the new paradigm of Russian education. The author clarifies the definition of discourse and its main characteristics from the standpoint of the methodology of teaching foreign languages.

Keywords: discourse; teaching a foreign language; communicative situation; bipolarity; motivation; characteristics of discourse; meta-meaning.

In linguistics, the concept of “discourse” is defined through the concept of “text” (Van Dijk), with the text often considered a part of a course or its basic unit. Recently, not only linguists but also scholars who focus on teaching foreign languages have shown interest in discourse. The relevance and popularity of the use of the concept of discourse in the methodology of teaching foreign languages can be attributed to its slightly modified meaning. Due to its complexity and multidimensionality, the concept of discourse continues to attract the attention of many researchers.

The very concept of “discourse” began to be used in the theory of teaching foreign languages in the 1970s. At that time, discourse was understood as a “coherent sequence of sentences or speech acts,” i.e., it was identified with the concept of “text.” In linguistics, the term discourse began to be widely used in the

early 1970s, initially in a meaning close to the term “functional style.” In both the Anglo-Saxon and European traditions, there was no stylistics as a separate branch of linguistics during this period, and scholars used the term discourse as a synonym for the word text. Later, however, linguists realized that discourse is not only a text but also a certain system behind it. As a result, the term discourse began to be used alongside the term functional style, which then completely replaced the previous one. The expansion of the scope of the concept of discourse has led to its incorporation into the theory of teaching foreign languages. According to researchers, borrowing the term discourse from linguistics is important, since, for a long time, the basic concept for the theory and practice of teaching foreign languages has been the text. It is around the text, and on its basis, that the educational process is built, new material is introduced, exercises are developed, etc.

The education system of Uzbekistan faces strategic tasks that cannot be solved without rethinking the theory and practice of teaching foreign languages. The expansion of opportunities for intercultural communication, due to the development of the global information space, is considered, at the present stage, a priority area of linguistic education. At the present stage in teaching a foreign language, tasks aimed at the formation of communicative and discursive competencies, which contribute to the achievement of the most important goal—the formation of a secondary linguistic personality with the ability to fully communicate in a given language—are becoming especially relevant. These competencies are particularly important when it comes to the use of literary texts in the training of future philologists and translators. Currently, the role of discursive competence, as an integral part of students’ foreign language communicative competence, is increasing. The purpose of this work is to analyze the concept of “discourse” from the perspectives of different sciences and authors, to show the importance of forming discursive competence among university students in the

learning process, and to emphasize its role in full-fledged intercultural communication.

Discourse is “the totality of everything that is spoken and understood in a certain specific situation in a particular era of the life of a given social group.” In this case, we are referring to general discourse. General discourse can be subdivided according to the theoretical-situational principle into private discourses based on a single topic—the situation. In turn, private discourse consists of specific discourses, which represent something that is said on a given topic at a specific period in time. As a result of the speech activity of specific native speakers, the following components are distinguished: its components are texts [1].

There are two main types of discourse in sociolinguistics: personal and institutional. In the first case, the speaker acts as an individual; in the second case, as a representative of a specific social institution. “Personal discourse exists in two main types: everyday and everyday communication.” Nowadays, the comprehensive influence of mass media on human communication leads to the unification of discourse genres, including everyday and institutional communication.

Institutional discourse is communication within a given framework of status-role relations. The following types of institutional discourse are used in the modern communicative space: political, diplomatic, administrative, legal, military, pedagogical, religious, mystical, medical, business, advertising, sports, scientific, scenic, and mass media [1,211]. For example, scientific discourse is characterized by a pronounced high degree of intertextuality; therefore, it is necessary to rely on specific texts and their concepts [2,132].

For the theory and practice of teaching and learning, it is important to understand discourse as a speech act that is not limited to the framework of a specific speech utterance. In the process of learning business English, business discourse acquires special importance, as it is an institutional type of discourse.

The main characteristics of business discourse include the participants in business communication, the situation, and the context. Business discourse is understood as the concrete embodiment of discourse realized by a specific group of people within a particular communicative situation, expressed in texts formed in special genres. In other words, it represents the verbal interaction of people in their professional activities [3,213].

In this work, discourse is understood as a complex communicative phenomenon that includes, in addition to the text, also extralinguistic factors (such as knowledge about the culture of the interlocutor, attitudes, and goals of the addressee). It can be said that discourse is an example of the realization of certain communicative intentions within the context of a specific communicative situation and in relation to a particular partner, expressed by appropriate linguistic means in that situation [4,110].

An important feature of the modern world is that the information and communication space is the sum of a wide variety of knowledge—both about the world itself and about facts and events produced by humans. The basic channel for transmitting this knowledge is a speech stream consisting of a variety of texts or a single global text. In the context of global communication, it becomes widespread and acquires specific features that distinguish it from all other types of communication, primarily in its inclusiveness and multilevel nature of the transmitted information [5,322]. It is precisely this global type of discourse, called mass informational discourse, that expresses the needs of modern society. A person must possess the skills of this discourse in order to align with modern society and find their place in it. Thus, we see that there is a direct connection between the interpretation of the concept of “discourse” and the classification of discourses by type, depending on the field of knowledge in which the term is interpreted. Despite differences in the definition of discourse, all researchers

recognize that it is associated with live speech and that there is no discourse outside of speech communication.

The creation of discourse is associated with the creativity of communicants, and therefore it is impractical to base learning on memorizing ready-made texts, which may not reflect the personality of the learner and may not be suitable for the specific communication situation.

It is obvious that discursive competence, which reflects the nature of cognitive, information-communicative, and reflexive activities, is an important element of the educational process, as it affects the success of speech communication functions. Competence of this kind is of particular importance in teaching, especially with the current transition to a personal paradigm in education. This is primarily due to the fact that, at the advanced level of scientific ideas, the key concept in teaching methodology is that of the linguistic personality, which includes a multicomponent, structurally ordered set of linguistic abilities, as well as the ability to produce and perceive speech messages. In this sense, discursive competence is one of the criteria for determining the level of development of a linguistic personality, as it includes such qualities as the use of communicative tools, mastery of techniques for organizing textual information, and a certain degree of proficiency in genre and structural elements of language [6,143].

Since discourse can be considered the realization of personal meanings in speech that provide the necessary motivation for communication, related to the personal need for self-expression, it can be argued that discursive competence contributes to the formation of the highest motivational and pragmatic levels of language proficiency [7,98].

How does discursive competence manifest itself? In the process of communication, it appears in the form of the ability to plan and manage discourse in order to have a communicative impact on the interlocutor. This ability is based on a set of abilities and properties that enable the performance of uniquely human

activities: to communicate by creating oral and written speech works that meet the goals and conditions of communication, to extract information from texts, and to perceive speech [8,145].

Thus, discursive competence, aimed at the perception and generation of discourses, can be considered a specific form of cognitive activity. To achieve the goals of learning, it is necessary to recognize that discursive competence contributes to the fulfillment of a number of educational tasks:

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